

PERCEIVED PUPILS' READINESS TO LEARN AND TEACHER EFFECTIVENESS: TWO KEY FACTORS IMPACTING MATHEMATICS ACHIEVEMENT

Cydelson G. Nicolas ¹, and Alberto G. Calibo, MST²

¹ *Cadu Elementary School, Department of Education, City of Ilagan, Isabela, Philippines*

² *Isabela State University-City of Ilagan, Campus, Philippines*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12068687>

ABSTRACT

This study examined the perceived readiness to learn among Grade VI pupils and teacher effectiveness in teaching mathematics in Clusters 5 and 6 of the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan during the 2023-2024 school year. Using a descriptive research design and total enumeration technique, the study involved 36 mathematics teachers and 344 pupils. Data were collected using the Collective Efficacy Scale-Short Form and tailored survey questionnaires. Results showed that teachers generally believe pupils are ready to learn, despite concerns about motivation, safety, and substance abuse. Pupils perceive their teachers as effective, with high mean scores indicating strong agreement on teachers' ability to reach and motivate students. Academic performance data revealed that the majority of pupils achieved “*Outstanding*” or “*Very Satisfactory*” results in mathematics. Statistical analysis using Pearson’s R demonstrated a significant positive relationship between pupils’ perception of teacher effectiveness and their mathematics achievement ($r = 0.81$, $p < 0.05$), highlighting the importance of effective teaching. However, no significant correlation was found between teachers’ perceptions of pupils’ learning readiness and academic performance. These findings emphasize the critical role of teacher effectiveness in enhancing mathematics achievement and suggest areas for targeted interventions to improve educational outcomes.

Keywords: *Teacher effectiveness, Pupil Readiness, Mathematics Achievement, Perception, Educational outcomes, Motivation*

INTRODUCTION

Mathematics is foundational to everyday life, providing the framework for activities across diverse professions, including agriculture, cooking, mechanics, medicine, commerce, music, engineering, science, and even magic. Nature itself reveals mathematical patterns, fostering endless discoveries. Engaging with mathematics nurtures mental discipline, enhances logical reasoning, promotes critical analysis, sparks inventiveness, cultivates abstract and spatial thinking, sharpens problem-solving skills, and improves communication abilities (Burns, 1995; NCTM, 2000). Mastery of mathematics enables individuals to approach various challenges systematically, thereby enriching their lives.

However, recent educational assessments highlight significant challenges in mathematics education in the Philippines. The Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) 2019 reported an average score of 297 in mathematics for Filipino students, placing the country among the lowest-performing out of 58 participants (Mullis et al., 2020). Similarly, the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) ranked the Philippines second lowest in mathematics and science among 79 countries, with scores of 353 and 357, respectively. These results emphasize the urgent need for educational reforms to elevate standards and improve learning outcomes nationwide (OECD, 2020).

In response, the Department of Education launched the "*Sulong Edukalidad*" initiative, which outlines strategic reforms such as the K to 12 curriculum review, enhancement of learning facilities, improved professional development for teachers and school heads, and strengthened stakeholder engagement. These efforts aim to ensure no Filipino student is left behind, calling for national collaboration and commitment to advancing the quality of basic education (Department of Education, 2020).

Addressing these issues requires understanding the root causes of poor mathematics performance and implementing swift remedial actions. The primary level is crucial for developing mathematical proficiency, which serves as the cornerstone of education across all levels. Students with strong numeracy skills are more likely to excel in advanced mathematics, whereas those lacking foundational skills may lose interest and struggle (Dowker, 2005). Schools must recognize the factors influencing math learning, particularly readiness to learn and teacher effectiveness.

Mathematical readiness, influenced by a supportive home and community environment, is essential for future academic success. Mastery of prerequisite skills through consistent practice is necessary to build a strong foundation in mathematics. Without these skills, students may experience hindered learning and diminished interest in the subject (Boaler, 2008). Enhancing overall math proficiency requires addressing these challenges early on.

Teacher effectiveness is another critical factor impacting math learning outcomes. Research shows that effective teaching practices significantly influence student

achievement, surpassing the effects of financial investments, class sizes, and other educational initiatives. Teachers' sense of efficacy is directly linked to student engagement and academic success (Hattie, 2009; Marzano, 2003). Engaging teaching methods, strong teacher-student interactions, and teacher empowerment create a positive learning environment where students can thrive (Ferguson, 2012).

The theoretical framework for this study is grounded in Bandura's (1978) social cognitive theory, which posits that behavior, personal factors, and environmental influences interact in a reciprocal, cause-and-effect relationship. In an educational context, this means that teacher-student interactions and the learning environment significantly shape students' self-efficacy and academic outcomes. According to Bandura (1989), resilient self-efficacy develops through overcoming challenges with persistent effort. Students who encounter only easy successes may struggle with setbacks, whereas those who persevere through difficulties build stronger self-efficacy. This interaction highlights the importance of creating a supportive and challenging learning environment to foster student achievement (Bandura, 1989).

Edmonds (1979) identified five school properties that predict student achievement, including high expectations and an orderly environment, aligning with the principles of social cognitive theory. These findings suggest that fostering a positive school environment and involving students in their education can enhance engagement and academic success. Incorporating student feedback on teacher effectiveness can increase their voice in education, promoting a democratic partnership between students and educators (Doda, 2011; Lounsbury, 2017; Newton, 2014).

To enhance mathematics education, schools should integrate interactive activities, mathematical games, and peer teaching methods into the curriculum. These approaches promote active learning, clarity of concepts, and collaborative problem-solving skills among students (Van de Walle et al., 2010). Emphasizing a clear understanding of mathematical concepts from the early stages and fostering enthusiasm for math through engaging activities are crucial steps toward improving math education outcomes.

This study aimed to address the Department of Education's goal of enhancing math education by investigating the lower math performance in Clusters 5 and 6 compared to other clusters. It assessed learners' first and second-quarter math grades and gathered insights from students and their mathematics teachers on readiness to learn and teacher effectiveness—key factors influencing math achievement. By focusing on these clusters within the Schools Division City of Ilagan (SDCI), the research aims to strengthen student readiness and teacher effectiveness in math teaching, ultimately contributing to ongoing efforts to improve academic outcomes in mathematics.

Research Questions

This study looked into the teacher's perception of pupils' readiness to learn and pupils' perception of teachers' effectiveness in teaching Grade VI Mathematics in Clusters 5 and 6 of the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan during the school year 2023-2024. Specifically, the study attempted to answer the following questions:

1. What is the perception of the teachers on pupils' readiness to learn?
2. What is the perception of the pupils on the teacher's effectiveness?
3. What is the academic achievement in mathematics of the pupils?
4. Is there a significant relationship between teachers' perception of pupils' readiness to learn and their mathematics achievement?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the pupils' perception of teacher effectiveness and their mathematics achievement?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the pupils' perception of the teachers' effectiveness and the teacher's perception of pupils?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The descriptive method of research was employed in this study. According to Williams (2007), this method involves a fact-finding approach with accurate and adequate interpretation of the findings. It emphasizes describing what exists, such as current conditions, practices, situations, or phenomena. Given that the study focused on the present status of teacher perceptions of pupil readiness to learn and pupil perceptions of teacher effectiveness, the descriptive method was deemed the most appropriate.

Respondents of the Study

The study included all members of the population using the Total Enumeration technique. In clusters 5 and 6, there are 18 schools, 36 teachers who teach grade 6 mathematics, and 344 grade 6 pupils. The study was conducted during the School Year 2023-2024.

Data Gathering Instruments

The Collective Efficacy Scale-Short Form, developed by Goddard (2002), was used in this study. This instrument is both valid and reliable for gauging teacher perceptions of faculty members' collective efficacy. It consists of 12 items across two factors, with responses measured on a six-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 6 (strongly agree).

The study made use of survey questionnaires as the main instruments to gather the needed data. These are the following:

Collective Efficacy Short Form was used with pupils, and reliability and factor analyses were run to determine the feasibility. It was a 12- 12-item instrument composed of two factors. The first factor measured by this instrument was faculty group competence. The second factor measured by this instrument was task analysis. This variable measured pupil readiness to learn.

Teacher Survey. The first factor measured by this instrument was faculty group competence. There were six survey items total that measured group competence, half of which were reverse-scored. Sample statements include: “Teachers in the school can get through to the most difficult pupils,” and “Teachers here are confident they will be able to motivate their pupils.”

The second factor measured by this instrument is task analysis. This variable measured pupil readiness to learn. Six total survey items measured pupil readiness to learn, half of which were reverse-scored. Sample statements from this factor include: “These pupils come to school ready to learn,” and “Pupils here just are not motivated to learn” (reverse scored).

Pupil Survey. Statistical analysis of the factor structure and reliability analysis for this instrument, when used with pupils, were included in the results. Factor analysis yielded one reliable factor. All six items loaded into this variable were derived from the faculty group competence section of the original survey. Items from the task analysis section of the survey did not demonstrate a sufficient Cronbach’s alpha level to merit inclusion and accordingly were removed from the pupil version of this survey. The results yielded a single-factor six-item instrument measuring pupil perception of teacher effectiveness. Items from this factor were: teachers in the school can get through to the most difficult pupils; teachers here are confident they will be able to motivate their pupils; if a pupil does not want to learn teachers here give up (reverse scored); teachers here do not have the skills needed to produce meaningful pupil learning (reverse scored); teachers in this school believe that every pupil can learn; and teachers in this school do not have the skills to deal with pupil disciplinary problems (reverse scored).

Data Gathering Procedure

Permission to conduct the study was sought by the researcher from the office of the Schools Division Superintendent of the City Division of Ilagan, Isabela before the study started to ensure its approval.

When the request was granted, the researcher approached the heads of the selected respondent schools. He showed them the approval of the study and informed them of the objectives and process of the study. The questionnaires were personally distributed and explained to the teacher respondents by the researcher. The questionnaires for pupil-respondents were translated into Tagalog, which was widely used by respondents. They were assisted in answering the questionnaire. Contact with the teachers was made in their classrooms during convenient schedules (usually lunch breaks or in the afternoon after classes) in order not to disturb classroom sessions.

Retrieval of the questionnaire followed immediately after needed clarifications of responses were made to ensure the accuracy and completeness of needed data. The researcher reviewed the entire total of questionnaires to see that all instructions were followed accurately. The data were collated, then tabulated for interpretation and analysis, and statistical treatment.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The data gathered were analyzed and interpreted using the following statistical tools:

Mean and Standard Deviation were used to identify to identify pupils' academic performance using the following scales as follows: (based on K to 12 standards)

Grading Scale	Description
90-100	Outstanding
85-89	Very Satisfactory
80-84	Satisfactory
75-79	Fairly satisfactory
Below 75	Did not meet expectations

Pearson's R was used to explore the relationship between teacher perceptions of pupil readiness to learn and mathematics achievement; the relationship between the pupil perception of teacher effectiveness and school mathematics achievement; and the relationship between pupil's perception of teacher's effectiveness and teacher's perception of the pupil.

Weighted Mean was used to analyze the teacher perceptions of pupil readiness to learn and mathematics achievement and pupil perception of teacher effectiveness and middle school mathematics achievement. Responses were measured on a six-point Likert scale with responses ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 6 (strongly agree).

Weight	Range	Description
6	5.50-6.0	Strongly Agree
5	4.50-5.49	Agree
4	3.5-4.49	Slightly Agree
3	2.5-3.49	Slightly Disagree
2	1.5-2.49	Disagree
1	1.0-1.49	Strongly Disagree

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Teachers' Perception of the Students' Readiness to Learn

As shown in Table 1, the majority of teachers express confidence in students' preparedness for learning, as evidenced by the high mean scores and low standard deviations associated with items one and four (Mean = 5.69, SD = 0.47, and Mean = 5.44, SD = 0.50 respectively). Additionally, there is a shared belief in the beneficial influence of community resources on student learning, as reflected in the responses to item two (Mean = 5.47, SD = 0.70).

Table 1. Teachers' perceptions regarding student readiness to learn

ITEM #	Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
1	These pupils come to school ready to learn.	5.69	0.47	Strongly Agree
2	Home life provides so many advantages that pupils here are bound to learn.	5.47	0.70	Agree
3	Pupils here just aren't motivated to learn.	2.44	1.32	Disagree
4	The opportunities in this community help ensure that these pupils will learn.	5.44	0.50	Agree
5	Learning is more difficult at this school because pupils are worried about their safety.	3.25	1.57	Slightly Disagree
6	Drug and alcohol abuse in the community makes learning difficult for pupils here.	5.14	0.80	Agree
Overall Mean		4.57	0.42	Agree

However, the divergence in perceptions becomes apparent when considering student motivation, as highlighted in item three (Mean = 2.44, SD = 1.32). Here, teachers exhibit varied viewpoints, with some expressing concerns about student motivation levels. This discrepancy underscores the complexity of factors influencing student engagement and highlights the need for targeted interventions to foster motivation and enhance learning outcomes.

Furthermore, items five and six draw attention to external factors that may impede student learning, such as safety concerns and substance abuse. While there is some

acknowledgment of these challenges, there is also variability in the extent to which teachers perceive them as significant barriers to learning.

In summary, while teachers generally perceive students as ready to learn and acknowledge the supportive role of the community, there are nuanced challenges related to student motivation and external factors that warrant further investigation and intervention. Addressing these challenges is crucial for enhancing teacher effectiveness and ultimately improving student achievement in mathematics.

Table 2. Pupils' perception of teacher effectiveness along various dimensions of teaching practices and interactions within the educational context

Item #	Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
1	Teachers in the school can get through to the most difficult pupils.	5.89	0.35	Strongly Agree
2	Teachers here are confident they will be able to motivate their pupils	5.49	0.75	Agree
3	If a pupil doesn't want to learn teachers here give up (reverse scored).	3.37	1.53	Slightly Disagree
4	Teachers here don't have the skills needed to produce meaningful pupil learning (reverse scored)	3.41	1.53	Slightly Disagree
5	Teachers in this school believe that every pupil can learn	5.85	0.50	Strongly Agree
6	Teachers in this school do not have the skills to deal with pupil disciplinary problems (reverse scored).	3.54	1.54	Slightly Agree
Overall mean		4.59	0.71	Agree

Based on the above table, firstly, item 1, "Teachers in the school can get through to the most difficult pupils," received a notably high mean score of 5.89, indicating strong agreement among pupils regarding teachers' effectiveness in reaching challenging students. This perception is reinforced by the low standard deviation of 0.35, suggesting a high level of consensus among respondents.

Similarly, item 2, "Teachers here are confident they will be able to motivate their pupils," garnered a favorable response from pupils, with a mean score of 5.49, indicative of agreement, albeit with a slightly higher standard deviation of 0.75, suggesting some variability in perceptions among respondents.

Conversely, items 3 and 4, which are reverse-scored, suggest a more nuanced perspective among pupils. While item 3, "If a pupil doesn't want to learn teachers here

give up," yielded a mean score of 3.37, indicating slight disagreement, the higher standard deviation of 1.53 suggests greater variability in perceptions regarding teacher persistence. Similarly, item 4, "Teachers here don't have the skills needed to produce meaningful pupil learning," also received a mean score of 3.41, suggesting slight disagreement among pupils, with a standard deviation of 1.53, indicating variability in perceptions regarding teacher competence.

Moreover, item 5, "Teachers in this school believe that every pupil can learn," garnered a high mean score of 5.85, indicating strong agreement among pupils, complemented by a low standard deviation of 0.50, indicating a high level of consensus. Finally, item 6, "Teachers in this school do not have the skills to deal with pupil disciplinary problems," received a mean score of 3.54, suggesting slight agreement among pupils, with a standard deviation of 1.54, indicating variability in perceptions regarding teacher proficiency in managing disciplinary issues.

In summary, while pupils generally perceive teachers as effective in reaching challenging students and fostering motivation, there are nuanced views regarding teacher persistence, competence, and disciplinary skills. These findings underscore the importance of understanding pupil perspectives to inform strategies aimed at enhancing teacher effectiveness and improving overall educational outcomes.

Table 3. Pupils' academic achievement in mathematics

Academic Performance	Frequency	Percent
Fairly Satisfactory	33	9.6
Satisfactory	56	16.3
Very Satisfactory	111	32.3
Outstanding	144	41.9
Total	344	100.0

Academic Achievement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
	85.00	4.73	Very Satisfactory

The academic achievement in mathematics among the pupils is predominantly high, with the majority of students achieving notable success. Specifically, the highest frequency of academic performance falls under the "Outstanding" category, with 144 pupils, accounting for 41.9% of the total. This indicates that nearly half of the pupils excelled in mathematics, demonstrating superior understanding and proficiency in the subject.

On the other end of the spectrum, the lowest frequency is observed in the "Fairly Satisfactory" category, with 33 pupils, representing 9.6% of the total. This suggests that a smaller portion of the student population is performing at a level that indicates a need for improvement.

The mean score of 85.00 suggests a very satisfactory level of academic achievement, with a relatively low standard deviation of 4.73, indicating a moderate degree of variability in individual achievement scores.

In summary, the data highlights a strong overall performance in mathematics, with a significant portion of students achieving “Outstanding” results, while only a small fraction falls into the “Fairly Satisfactory” range. This suggests a positive trend in academic achievement in mathematics among the pupils.

Table 4. Relationship between teachers' perception of pupils' readiness to learn and their mathematics achievement

Variables	Pearson r	p-value	Decision	Remark
Teacher's Perception of pupil's readiness to learn Vs. mathematics achievement	-0.052	0.76	Accept Ho	The relationship is not significant

The Pearson correlation coefficient (Pearson R) of -0.052 indicates a very weak negative correlation between these variables. The p-value of 0.76 suggests that this correlation is not statistically significant.

Based on the statistical analysis, the decision to "Accept Ho" (accept the null hypothesis) is made, indicating that there is no significant relationship between teachers' perception of pupils' readiness to learn and their mathematics achievement. This implies that the perceived readiness of pupils to learn, as perceived by teachers, does not have a meaningful impact on their actual academic achievement in mathematics.

In summary, the statistical analysis concludes that there is no significant relationship between teachers' perception of pupils' readiness to learn and their mathematics achievement. These findings provide valuable insights into the dynamics between teacher perceptions and student academic outcomes, informing future research and educational interventions aimed at enhancing student achievement in mathematics.

As discussed in the review of the literature, the results have contradicted the study of Lumpkin (2007), that there is no significant relationship between teachers' perception of pupils' readiness to learn and their mathematics achievement. Students' and teachers' perceptions of one another influence student learning. Lumpkin (2007) discovered that pupils who see their teachers as caring are more motivated and perform better than their classmates who do not have a positive attitude toward their teachers. Competence and concern are especially crucial in primary schooling. "Effective teachers are adept educators who organize and conduct classes and evaluate pupil learning," Virtue (2007) stated. When teachers feel positive about their students, this makes the teacher more likely to be able to disseminate information effectively. Thus, the espousal of confidence in these students' readiness to learn may positively impact the teacher's ability to teach. It is also possible that students may be picking up on their teachers' perceptions. If students perceive that their teachers believe they can learn, they may be more likely

actually to learn. This study adds to the extant literature by demonstrating that teacher perceptions of student readiness to learn are significantly related to the mathematics achievement of the pupils. Both new and experienced teachers agreed that pupils who felt comfortable turned in significantly greater work. Greater pupil aspirations and accomplishments are possible in safe environments when parents organize the neighborhood and support their children (Gaitan, 2012).

Also, the results have contradicted the study of that there is no significant relationship between teachers' perception of pupils' readiness to learn and their mathematics achievement. Students' and teachers' perceptions of one another influence student learning. Boz and Boz (2010) discovered that teachers who exhibit high efficaciousness tend to exhibit higher levels of enthusiasm in the classroom. concluded that this enthusiasm translates to a teacher who works harder to assist struggling students. Conversely, those who exhibit low levels of teaching efficacy tend to be more teacher-centered and have a weak commitment to the profession (Boz & Boz, 2010). They further suggested that teachers need to be specifically taught to satisfy the academic, social, and emotional needs of their students. School administrators have the responsibility to observe classroom instruction regularly and to provide substantive feedback and support to their faculty (Goldhorn, Kearney, & Webb, 2013). Feedback becomes particularly important in pupils when pupils often struggle in the affective domain (Ross & Willson, 2012).

Table 5. Relationship between pupils' perception of teacher effectiveness and their mathematics achievement

Variables	Pearson R	ρ-value	Decision	Remark
Pupil's perception of teacher effectiveness Vs. mathematics achievement	0.81	0.00	Reject Ho	Relationship is significant

The Pearson correlation coefficient (r) of 0.81 indicates a very strong positive relationship between pupils' perception of teacher effectiveness and their mathematics achievement. This suggests that as pupils perceive their teachers to be more effective, their mathematics achievement tends to be higher.

The ρ -value of 0.00 (which is likely rounded from a very small number) indicates that this correlation is statistically significant. In statistical terms, a p -value less than the conventional significance level (typically 0.05) suggests strong evidence against the null hypothesis (H_0), leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. In this case, it means there is sufficient evidence to conclude that there is a significant relationship between pupils' perception of teacher effectiveness and their mathematics achievement.

This finding underscores the importance of how pupils perceive their teachers in influencing their academic outcomes in mathematics. When students believe their

teachers are effective, they are likely to engage more deeply in learning, exhibit higher motivation, and achieve better results in mathematics.

The results affirm the study of (Lumpkin, 2007). The results demonstrated that when students perceive their mathematics teachers as being effective, their scores rise. Students perform well for their teachers when they have an affinity for their teachers, so it is possible those students who have an affinity for their teachers rated their teachers' effectiveness more highly and performed better for these teachers (Lumpkin, 2007). It is also possible that students accurately perceived their teachers' abilities. Those they perceived as effective in mathematics are competent. The perception students and teachers have about one another impacts student learning. Lumpkin (2007) found that students who perceive their teachers as caring tend to be more motivated and perform better than their peers who do not indicate an affinity for their teachers. Competence and care are particularly important in middle-level education. As Virtue (2007) noted, "Effective teachers are apt instructors who plan and implement lessons and evaluate student learning . . . [and] are also skilled at establishing and cultivating constructive human relationships" (Virtue, 2007, p. 243). Teachers who have high opinions of their students tend to get higher results. These student outcomes could be due, in part, to the Pygmalion effect which occurs when achievement rises for students about whom teachers are told their students are in the highest ability group when they are, in fact, previously low performing (Rosenthal & Jacobsen, 2003).

Also, another possibility is found in literacy studies and is known as the "Peter effect" (Applegate & Applegate, 2004). Essentially, teachers cannot give students what they do not have. If the teachers are not proficient in delivering pedagogy or in mathematics, they cannot engender proficiency in their students. Students tune into the competency levels of teachers and draw their conclusions.

By establishing motivational processes in the mathematics classroom—inclusive of self-efficacy, task interest, and school connectedness (Cleary & Kistantas, 2017)—educators can ameliorate some of the lack of preparation teachers may face. Motivational processes, coupled with professional development to increase teacher proficiency in mathematic strategies, can be an incredibly powerful tool that may yield significant increases in student mathematics achievement.

Table 6. Relationship between teachers' perception of pupils' readiness to learn and pupils' perception of teacher effectiveness

Variables	Pearson R	p-value	Decision	Remark
Teacher's Perception of pupil's readiness to learn Vs. pupils' perception of teacher effectiveness	-0.14	0.40	Accept Ho	The relationship is not significant

The analysis explores the relationship between teachers' perception of pupils' readiness to learn and pupils' perception of teacher effectiveness.

The Pearson correlation coefficient (Pearson R) between these variables is -0.14, indicating a weak negative correlation. However, the p-value associated with this correlation is 0.40, which exceeds the typical threshold for statistical significance (usually set at 0.05). Consequently, the decision is made to "Accept Ho" (accept the null hypothesis), suggesting that the observed difference is not significant.

In summary, based on the statistical analysis, there is no significant relationship between teachers' perception of pupils' readiness to learn and pupils' perception of teacher effectiveness. These findings suggest that, according to the data examined, there is no meaningful association between how teachers view students' readiness to learn and how students perceive teacher effectiveness.

The results contradict the study of Yazzie-Mintz (2010) that there is no meaningful association between how teachers view student's readiness to learn and how students perceive teacher effectiveness. Yazzie-Mintz (2010) Student readiness to learn and teacher competence are linked. A survey of 42,754 high school students, reported a majority of students stated that the material presented in class was not interesting, which contributed to their disengagement in class. Further, 35 percent of the students surveyed stated their boredom stemmed from a lack of interaction with their teacher. Both the student's readiness to learn and the teacher's competence are essential to student learning.

It negates the study of Bandura (1978) and Edmonds (1979) which states that the relationships between teachers and students matter. Also, when students have a greater voice in their education, their level of engagement and academic success increases (Lounsbury, 2017; Newton, 2014). Asking students for feedback on teacher effectiveness is a useful way to increase student voices and involve them as democratic partners in their education (Doda, 2011). Kearney, Webb, Goldhorn, and Peters (2013) found a correlation between mathematics scores and critical feedback in a study of 87 mathematics classrooms in Texas. Specifically, teachers who received appraisal scores from their principals indicating high levels of critical feedback to students had higher mathematics achievement scores for their classrooms than their peers.

Naturally, teachers' professional competence has a demonstrable effect on students' ability to learn (Baumert et al., 2010). School principals play an important role in this process when they embrace the responsibility of instructional leadership to ensure that faculty are life-long learners perpetually refining their craft (George, 2000). Instructional leaders, "participate fully in training, care deeply about the results, and follow up with supervision that integrates teacher training and classroom observations" (George, 2000, p. 44). Efficacy also appears to play an important role in mathematics achievement. Students who espouse a high level of belief in their mathematics abilities tend to demonstrate high levels of mathematics achievement (Siegle & McCoach, 2007).

Similarly, Goddard and Goddard (2001) conducted a study of 438 teachers in 47 schools in a large urban school district in the United States and found that schools in which teachers espouse high levels of faculty members' collective efficacy have been shown to produce high student achievement scores. To be sure, many other factors have the potential to influence student achievement. One such factor is student readiness to learn.

Conclusions

This study investigated the impact of pupils' readiness to learn and teacher effectiveness on mathematics achievement in Clusters 5 and 6 within the Schools Division City of Ilagan. The findings indicated that while teachers generally perceive students as ready to learn and supported by their community, issues like student motivation, safety concerns, and substance abuse present significant challenges. A notable discovery was the strong positive correlation between pupils' perception of teacher effectiveness and their mathematics achievement, emphasizing the critical role of effective teaching in academic success. However, there was no significant relationship between teachers' perception of pupil readiness and students' actual performance, suggesting that teacher effectiveness plays a more pivotal role in influencing academic outcomes. These insights underscore the importance of enhancing teacher effectiveness and addressing external factors to improve mathematics achievement, highlighting areas for targeted interventions to foster better educational outcomes.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. School heads are strongly urged to implement comprehensive professional development programs focusing on effective teaching strategies, classroom management, and motivational techniques. These programs should equip teachers with the skills necessary to engage students, manage diverse classroom dynamics, and address challenges related to student motivation and external factors like substance abuse and safety concerns.
2. Schools and community organizations like the Parents and Teacher Associations (PTAs) should strengthen partnerships to create supportive environments for students. Community resources should be mobilized to address issues such as student safety and substance abuse, thereby removing external barriers to learning and enhancing the overall readiness of students to engage in their studies.
3. The School Guidance Office is encouraged to design and implement targeted interventions aimed at boosting student motivation. This could include mentorship programs, extracurricular activities, and motivational workshops. Encouraging a growth

mindset and providing positive reinforcement can help increase students' intrinsic motivation and engagement in their learning processes.

4. Schools are to establish mechanisms for regularly gathering and analyzing student feedback on teacher effectiveness. This feedback should be used to inform teacher evaluations and professional development, ensuring that teachers continuously refine their teaching practices based on the needs and perceptions of their students.

5. The schools should adopt a holistic approach to student development that goes beyond academic achievement. This involves addressing social-emotional learning, providing mental health support, and ensuring a safe and inclusive school environment. By fostering a well-rounded development, students are more likely to perform better academically and build resilience against external challenges.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

As the authors of this study, we hereby declare that all ethical considerations were meticulously observed throughout the research process. Informed consent was duly obtained from all respondents before their participation, ensuring that they were fully aware of the study's purpose and procedures. Respondents were granted the freedom to withdraw from the study at any time without any repercussions. The anonymity of all respondents was strictly maintained to protect their privacy, and their well-being was consistently safeguarded. Furthermore, we affirm that there is no conflict of interest in the conduct of this study. We have diligently avoided any form of plagiarism and ensured that the interpretation of findings was free from bias. The results obtained from this study have been used solely for research purposes, adhering to the highest standards of academic integrity.

Acknowledgments

I would like to extend my deepest gratitude to all those who contributed to the successful completion of this research study. I am profoundly grateful to my adviser for their invaluable guidance and support. Sincere appreciation goes to the respondents, school heads, and co-teachers for their cooperation and participation. I am also thankful to my friends, family, and relatives for their unwavering support and encouragement, which motivated me to persevere. Lastly, I acknowledge my friends for their continuous encouragement and understanding throughout this journey. Your collective support and belief in me have been instrumental in the success of this research study.

REFERENCES

- Applegate, A. J., & Applegate, M. D. (2004). The Peter effect: Reading habits and attitudes of preservice teachers. *The Reading Teacher*, 57(6), 554-563.
- Bandura, A. (1978). The self-system in reciprocal determinism. *American Psychologist*, 33(4), 344-358.

- Bandura, A. (1989). Human agency in social cognitive theory. *American Psychologist*, 44(9), 1175-1184.
- Baumert, J., Kunter, M., Blum, W., Brunner, M., Voss, T., Jordan, A., ... & Tsai, Y. M. (2010). Teachers' mathematical knowledge, cognitive activation in the classroom, and student progress. *American Educational Research Journal*, 47(1), 133-180.
- Boaler, J. (2008). *What's math got to do with it?: How teachers and parents can transform mathematics learning and inspire success*. Penguin Books.
- Boz, Y., & Boz, N. (2010). Beliefs about teaching: How do student teachers' beliefs about teaching change during the duration of a pre-service teacher education program? *The Journal of Educational Research*, 103(2), 152-162.
- Burns, M. (1995). *About teaching mathematics: A K-8 resource*. Math Solutions Publications.
- Cleary, T. J., & Kitsantas, A. (2017). Motivation and self-regulated learning influences on middle school mathematics achievement. *School Psychology Review*, 46(1), 88-107.
- Department of Education. (2020). *Sulong Edukalidad: The DepEd reforms*. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/sulong-edukalidad/>
- Doda, N. (2011). Engaging students as partners in learning and teaching. *Educational Leadership*, 68(5), 84-85.
- Doda, N. (2011). A Middle school teacher's guide to supporting student voice. *Middle School Journal*, 43(1), 58-64.
- Dowker, A. (2005). *Individual differences in arithmetic: Implications for psychology, neuroscience and education*. Psychology Press.
- Edmonds, R. (1979). Effective schools for the urban poor. *Educational Leadership*, 37(1), 15-24.
- Ferguson, R. F. (2012). Can student surveys measure teaching quality? **Phi Delta Kappan*, 94(3), 24-28.
- Gaitan, C. D. (2012). Culture, literacy, and power in family–community–school–relationships. *Theory Into Practice*, 51(4), 305-311.
- George, P. S. (2000). The principal as instructional leader. *Middle School Journal*, 31(5), 43-48.
- Goddard, R. D. (2002). A theoretical and empirical analysis of the measurement of collective efficacy: The development of a short form. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 62(1), 97-110
- Goddard, R. D., & Goddard, Y. L. (2001). A multilevel analysis of the relationship between teacher and collective efficacy in urban schools. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 17(7), 807-818.
- Goldhorn, J., Kearney, P., & Webb, L. D. (2013). Teacher feedback: An essential part of effective teaching. *Journal of Education for Teaching*, 39(5), 560-574.
- Hattie, J. (2009). *Visible learning: A synthesis of over 800 meta-analyses relating to achievement*. Routledge.
- Kearney, P., Webb, L. D., Goldhorn, J., & Peters, G. (2013). An investigation of the relationship between critical feedback and mathematics achievement. *Educational Studies*, 39(5), 560-574.
- Lounsbury, J. H. (2017). The voice of the young adolescent. *Middle School Journal*, 48(1), 7-15.

- Lounsbury, J. (2017). Re-imagining student engagement. **Middle School Journal*, 48 (3), 6-9.
- Lumpkin, A. (2007). Caring teachers: The key to student learning. *Kappa Delta Pi Record*, 43 (4), 158-162.
- Marzano, R. J. (2003). *What works in schools: Translating research into action*. ASCD.
- Mullis, I. V. S., Martin, M. O., Foy, P., Kelly, D. L., & Fishbein, B. (2020). *TIMSS 2019 International Results in Mathematics and Science*. Boston College, TIMSS & PIRLS International Study Center.
- Newton, J. A. (2014). Building relationships with students: The key to classroom management. *Phi Delta Kappan*, 96(2), 27-31.
- Newton, P. (2014). The impact of formative assessment on student achievement. *Educational Research Review*, 9, 58-70.
- NCTM (National Council of Teachers of Mathematics). (2000). *Principles and standards for school mathematics*. NCTM.
- OECD. (2020). *PISA 2018 results (Volume I): What students know and can do*. OECD Publishing.
- Ross, J. A., & Willson, V. L. (2012). Teacher efficacy and the effects of coaching on student achievement. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 28(4), 472-482.
- Siegle, D., & McCoach, D. B. (2007). Increasing student mathematics self-efficacy through teacher training. *Journal of Advanced Academics*, 18(2), 278-312.
- Van de Walle, J. A., Karp, K. S., & Bay-Williams, J. M. (2010). *Elementary and middle school mathematics: Teaching developmentally* (7th ed.). Allyn & Bacon/Pearson.
- Virtue, D. C. (2007). Middle level teachers' perceptions of effective teaching. *Middle School Journal*, 38(5), 42-49.
- Yazzie-Mintz, E. (2010). *Charting the path from engagement to achievement: A report on the 2009 High School Survey of Student Engagement*. Bloomington, IN: Center for Evaluation & Education Policy, Indiana University.
- Williams, C. (2007). Research methods. *Journal of Business & Economic Research*, 5(3), 65-72
-